

Original Research Article

Distribution of okra root rot (*Fusarium solani*) in district of Peshawar and Nowshera and characterization of different isolates

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Abstract

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The root rot of okra (*Fusarium solani*) was distributed up to 32.09 to 91.14 % in ten different okra growing regions of District Peshawar and Nowshera. The highest disease severity with maximum (91.14 %) percent mortality was reported by isolate NI₂ from Garhi Momin and lowest (32.09 %) by isolate NI₄ from Balu. *In vitro*, all the isolates were observed to be significantly different by their characterization at different pH levels (5.0, 5.6 and 9.0). All the isolates grew well at pH level of 5.0 with maximum colony diameter of 76.73 mm, 1.97 g of fresh biomass and 2.29×10^6 ml⁻¹ of spore production and at pH 5.6 (77.14 mm, 1.89 g and 2.16×10^6 ml⁻¹). The maximum growth among the isolates was attained by isolate NI₂ with 96.67 mm of colony diameter, 2.52 g of biomass and 3.23×10^6 ml⁻¹ of sporulation and lowest by NI₄ (57.89 mm, 0.87 g and 0.76×10^6). *In vitro*, Dithane M-45 was found as the most effective fungicide in controlling *Fusarium solani* (6.87 mm, 0.24 g, 0.09×10^6 ml⁻¹) than Aliette (75.20 mm, 1.54 g, 1.54×10^6 ml⁻¹) and Copper oxychloride (69.10 mm, 1.55 g, 1.45×10^6 ml⁻¹) as compared to control (84.67 mm, 2.18 g, 2.14×10^6 ml⁻¹). The isolate NI₂ found as the most aggressive isolate by exhibiting the maximum growth in Aliette and Copper oxychloride amended culture media as observed in control (non poisoned).

Key words: Okra, Root rot, *Fusarium solani*, isolates, *in vitro* and characterization.

INTRODUCTION

Okra (*Abelmoschus esculentus* L) locally known as "bhindi" is one of the most important summer vegetables in Pakistan. It is grown in all parts of the tropics and during summer in the warmer parts of the temperate region (Baloch, 1994). It is the most widely known and utilized species of the family Malvaceae (Bayer and Kubitzki, 2003; Naveed *et al.*, 2009). In Pakistan, okra occupied an area of 14855 ha with a total production of 112983 tones, while in KP, it occupied an area of 1957 ha with a total production of 15630 tones (MINFAL, 2014).

Okra plants are attacked by a number of soil borne diseases caused by different fungi such as, *Fusarium*

solani, *Macrophomina phaseolina*, *Rhizoctonia bataticola*, *R. solani*, *Pythium butleri*, *Phytophthora palmivora*, *Cercospora abelmoschii* and *Erysiphe cichoracearum* (Mithal, 2006). Among them, *Fusarium solani* (Mart) Sacc., the causal organism of okra root rot (Rahim *et al.* 1992; Haq *et al.*, 1996) has been considered as one of the most destructive pathogens (Mithal, 2006). It has a wide host range and known to decrease both the quantity and quality of major crops including tomato (Parveen *et al.*, 1993), soybean (Mousa, 1994) and other vegetables (Ghaffar, 1995). Its incidence range from 10-80% and maximum 55-80% in the crop grown on small scale as kitchen/home gardening and minimum from 10-45% in

the crop sown on large scale under field conditions (Mithal, 2006).

The plants infected with *Fusarium solani* show dark brown to black discoloration from the base of stem. Severely infected plants become dead, their roots turn dark brown in color and are badly damaged. The fungus perpetuates in the soil or gets attached to infected plants. Root rot may affect individual plant or a group of plants in patches spreading rapidly under optimum conditions (Mithal, 2006). *Fusarium* root rot is favored by higher soil temperatures (optimum 25°C to 30°C) and moderate soil moisture (Malvick, 2002). The disease severity depends upon cultural and climatic factors such as plant spacing, soil moisture, depth of planting and stress from low or high temperatures. The effect of root rot becomes most apparent during seedling stage (Aviles *et al.*, 2003).

The disease can be managed through cultural practices such as time of sowing, appropriate row and plant spacing, crop rotation, seed rate, water and other nutritional requirements (Jhonson *et al.*, 1997). Among them, time of sowing plays the most important role (Naz *et al.*, 2009). The use of fungicides such as Benomyl and Captan is also effective against the disease (Ghaffar, 1993). The antagonistic fungi and bacteria (*Trichoderma harzianum*, *Trichoderma viride* and *Bacillus subtilis*) used as biocontrol agents have also been reported to reduce the percentage of infected plants and severity of the disease (Mithal, 2006). *Fusarium* species are highly variable because of their genetic make up and changes in the environment in which they grow (Nelson *et al.*, 1983). Due to its high adaptability to environmental conditions, the variation exists among isolates of the pathogen. As far as better management is concerned, the exact identification and characterization of the isolates is very important to formulate effective control strategies accordingly.

Keeping in view the importance of the disease and losses it causes, the present study was initiated with the objectives, (1) to find out the distribution of okra root rot in the okra growing regions of district Peshawar and Nowshera and (2) to study the *in vitro* effect of different pH levels and fungicides on the mycelia growth, spore concentration and biomass on various isolates of the pathogen.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Seedling mortality (%) due to okra root rot in District Peshawar and Nowshera

A survey was conducted in the okra growing regions of District Peshawar (Acheni Payan, Palosi, Chamkani, Jogian and Budhni) and Nowshera (Akbarpura, Garhi Momin, Zakhi Charbagh, Balu and Taru Jabba) during the 2012 growing season of the crop. At each location, five fields were randomly selected for measuring the

disease severity. In each field, seedling mortality (%) was calculated at five places. Seedling mortality (%) was calculated on one meter square patch in each spot by using the following formula.

$$\text{Seedlings Mortality (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of root rotted seedlings}}{\text{Total Number of seedlings per m}^2} \times 100$$

Infected seedlings were collected from each location and were brought to the laboratory of Plant Pathology, The University of Agriculture Peshawar for further studies.

Isolation and identification of the pathogen from diseased okra seedlings

Collected okra seedlings from ten different areas of District Peshawar and Nowshera were cut into small pieces, surface sterilized with 0.1% solution of Mercuric chloride (HgCl₂) for 15-30 seconds, rinsed three times with sterilized distilled water to remove the extra disinfectants and blotted dry. The treated pieces were then placed on potato dextrose agar (PDA) medium in Petri dishes under aseptic conditions, incubated at 25°C and observed regularly for the mycelia growth. The potato dextrose agar medium was prepared by using the standard procedure (for one liter of PDA, 250 g peeled potato, 20 g agar and 20 g dextrose) and was sterilized in autoclave for 20 minutes at 121°C. Streptomycin sulphate was added into the medium before pouring into the Petri plates to inhibit the bacterial growth. The pathogen was identified by using the pictorial guide of Tousson and Nelson (1976). The isolated fungus was sub cultured for further studies.

In vitro study

Effect of different pH levels on the mycelia growth, spore concentration and biomass of different isolates of the pathogen

An *in vitro* experiment was conducted to determine the effect of three different pH levels (5.0, 5.6 and 9.0) on the mycelia growth, spore concentration and biomass of the ten different isolates of the pathogen collected from various regions of district Peshawar and Nowshera. The potato dextrose agar medium was adjusted to different pH levels with the help of pH meter. After sterilization, the media was poured into Petri plates and the inoculum plug of equal diameter (5 mm) of each isolate was inoculated at the centre of plate. The data was recorded on radial mycelia growth after 5 and 10 days of the incubation at 25°C. The micro-conidial sporulation per ml was recorded in 10 days old culture of isolates with the help of haemocytometer. The fresh biomass (g) was obtained by adding the equal diameter of inoculum of each isolate in

Table 1. Disease distribution of ten isolates of okra root rot collected from ten different locations of district Peshawar and Nowshera.

Districts	Isolates	Field 1	Field 2	Field 3	Field 4	Field 5	Mean
Peshawar	PI ₁	75.87 GHI	64.78 MNO	74.34 G-J	65.35 MN	72.05 IJK	70.48 E
	PI ₂	74.34 J	75.87 GHI	75.98 GHI	77.72 FG	78.54 EFG	76.48 D
	PI ₃	52.76 Q	58.62 P	57.14 PQ	53.75 Q	58.85 P	56.22 G
	PI ₄	83.33 D	82.75 DE	82.71 DE	77.26 GH	72.56 H-K	79.71 C
	PI ₅	43.43 R	37.84 ST	41.87 RS	36.00 TU	41.67 RS	40.16 H
Nowshera	sNI ₁	86.42 BCD	86.03 BCD	84.74 CD	80.54 D	82.55 DEF	84.65 B
	NI ₂	93.57 A	89.70 AB	89.37 ABC	92.73 A	90.31 AB	91.14 A
	NI ₃	61.12 NOP	70.34 JKL	74.69 G-J	74.59 G-J	70.34 JKL	69.89 E
	NI ₄	34.83 TU	31.39 UV	35.86 TU	28.55 V	29.80 V	32.09 I
	NI ₅	59.96 OP	57.02 PQ	65.89 LMN	65.84 LMN	66.48 LM	63.04 F
	Mean	66.57 B	65.27 B	68.26 A	66.04 B	65.79 B	66.39

LSD for Locations (L)	2.16
LSD for Fields (F)	1.53
LSD for L×F	4.83
CV (%)	5.83

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhi Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

flasks containing potato dextrose broth adjusted to different pH levels. The flasks were incubated at 25°C and the data were recorded after 15 days. For this, a Completely Randomized two factor factorial design was framed with three replications.

***In vitro* efficacy of fungicides on different isolates of the pathogen**

A Completely Randomized two factor factorial experiment having three replications was designed to determine the *in vitro* efficacy of three different fungicides (Aliette, Copper oxychloride and Dithan M-45) @ 1000 ppm (Nisa *et al*, 2011) against ten different isolates of the pathogen collected from District Peshawar and Nowshera. Fungicides were incorporated into potato dextrose agar medium after sterilization and then poured into petri dishes. The inoculum plug of equal diameter for each isolate was placed at the centre of Petri plate. One treatment was kept as untreated check for each isolate. The plates were then incubated at 25°C and the data on colony diameter was taken after 5 and 10 days of incubation. The data on micro-conidial concentration per ml was recorded in 10 days old culture of isolates by using haemocytometer. For fresh biomass (g), the equal inoculum of the isolates was added in potato dextrose broth flasks which were treated with different fungicides. The data were recorded after 15 days of incubation at 25°C.

RESULTS

Disease distribution (Okra root rot) in District Peshawar and Nowshera

Significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) were observed among the ten isolates of *Fusarium solani* of district Peshawar and Nowshera (Table 1). In District Nowshera, the disease was recorded most severe with highest (91.14 %) seedling mortality in Garhi Momin (NI₂) followed by Akbarpura (NI₁) as 84.65 % while lowest as 32.09 % in Balu (NI₄). In district Peshawar, the maximum disease severity with highest (79.71 %) seedling mortality was recorded in Jogian (PI₄) followed by Palosi (PI₂) as 76.48 % and lowest (40.16 %) in Budhni (PI₅).

Effect of different pH levels on colony diameter after five days of incubation

Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in the colony diameter of isolates of *Fusarium solani* were observed at different pH levels. The maximum (80.56 mm) colony diameter was recorded by NI₂ followed by NI₁ (65.00 mm) and NI₅ (58.11 mm), whereas the lowest colony diameter was observed in case of NI₄ (31.67 mm). All the isolates grew well at pH level 5.0 (57.03 mm) and 5.6 (56.73 mm), whereas the lowest colony diameter (45.63 mm) was recorded at pH 9.0. In case of interaction combinations between different pH levels (5.0, 5.6 and 9.0) and five isolates of district Peshawar, the maximum (57.00 mm) radial colony diameter was measured in case of isolate

Figure 1. (A) Figure showing effect of different pH levels (5.0, 5.6 and 9.0) on the colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *Fusarium solani* collected from different locations of District Peshawar after five (5) days of incubation at 25°C.

Figure 2 (B) Figure showing effect of different pH levels (5.0, 5.6 and 9.0) on the colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *Fusarium solani* collected from different locations of district Nowshera after five (5) days of incubation at 25°C.

PI₄ and PI₅ at 5.6 level of pH followed by isolate PI₂ and PI₃ (54.00 mm) at pH 5.0, whereas the lowest colony diameter was recorded (35.00 mm) by PI₄ at 9.0 pH level. The isolate PI₁ was found efficient in utilizing all the pH levels by exhibiting radial colony growth as 45.00 mm, 51.00 mm and 43.00 mm at 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 levels of pH (Figure 1, A).

Contrary to the above results, the different isolates of district Nowshera exhibited maximum radial colony growth almost at every pH level. In case of interaction combinations between different pH levels and isolates of different locations, the isolate NI₂ exhibited maximum (85.00 mm, 82.33 mm and 74.30 mm) radial colony growth at 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 pH levels (Figure 2, B). The

Table 2. Effect of different pH levels on colony diameter (mm) of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani* after five days of incubation.

Districts	Isolates	pH levels			Mean
		5.0	5.6	9.0	
Peshawar	PI ₁	45.00 L	51.00 JK	43.00 M	46.33 G
	PI ₂	54.00 H	53.00 HI	*50.00 K	52.33 D
	PI ₃	54.00 H	52.00 IJ	*45.00 L	50.33 F
	PI ₄	40.00 N	57.00 G	35.00 O	44.00 H
	PI ₅	53.00 HI	57.00 G	44.00 M	51.33 E
Nowshera	NI ₁	75.00 C	70.00 B	50.00 K	65.00 B
	NI ₂	85.00 A	82.33 B	74..30 C	80.56 A
	NI ₃	60.00 F	50.00 K	45.00 L	51.67 DE
	NI ₄	40.00 N	35.00 O	20.00 P	31.67 I
	NI ₅	64.33 E	60.00 F	50.00 K	58.11 C
	Mean	57.03A	56.73 A	45.63 B	53.13

LSD for Fields (F) 0.86

LSD for Isolates (T) 0.47

LSD for I×T 1.49

CV (%) 1.72

*Patches were formed in radial colony growth.

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhi Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

Figure 3 (C) Petri plates showing effect of different pH levels (5.6, 5.0 and 9.0) on colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *F. solani* on PDA after ten (10) days of incubation at 25 °C, collected from different locations of District Peshawar.

isolate NI₁ showed radial colony growth (75.00 mm and 70.00 mm) at 5.0 and 5.6 pH levels, whereas the isolate NI₄ showed minimum (20.00 mm) radial colony growth at 9.0 pH. In interaction combinations, the isolates accomplished maximum radial colony growth at 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 pH levels (Table 2).

Effect of different pH levels on colony diameter of *F. solani* after 10 days of Incubation at 25°C

The isolates showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) at different pH levels. The maximum colony diameter (96.67 mm) was exhibited by NI₂ followed by NI₃ (80.78 mm)

Figure 4. (D) Petri plates showing effect of different pH levels (5.6, 5.0 and 9.0) on colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *F. solani* on PDA after ten (10) days of incubation at 25 °C, collected from different locations of District Nowshera.

and NI₁ (78.26 mm), while the lowest colony diameter was accomplished by NI₄ (57.89 mm). The isolates grew best at pH 5.0 and 5.6 than 9.0 with 76.73 mm, 77.14 mm and 68.13 mm. In case of interactions combinations between different pH levels and isolates of District Peshawar, the maximum (80.00 mm) radial colony growth of isolate PI₁ was recorded at 5.6 pH level followed by PI₄ (78.00 mm) and PI₅ (75.16 mm) at the same pH level (5.6). On the other hand, the isolate PI₅ exhibited minimum (61.37 mm) radial colony growth at pH level of 9.0 (Figure 3).

The isolates of district Nowshera exhibited maximum radial colony growth at every pH level (Figure 4). In case of interaction combinations between different pH levels and isolates, the maximum (100.00 mm and 90.00 mm) radial colony growth was accomplished by the isolate NI₂ at 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 level of pH whereas the isolate NI₃,

NI₁ and NI₅ exhibited radial colony growth of 85.00 mm, 83.78 mm and 80.00 mm at pH 5.0. The isolate NI₁ and NI₃ gives maximum (81.00 mm and 80.00 mm) radial colony growth at pH 5.6. On the other hand, the isolate NI₄ exhibited minimum (51.67 mm) radial colony growth at 9.0 level of pH. In interaction combinations, the isolates accomplished minimum radial colony growth at 9.0 pH level as compared to 5.6 and 5.0 pH level (Table 2).

Effect of different pH levels on fresh biomass (g) after 15 days of incubation

The isolates were found significantly different ($P < 0.05$) by

the effect of different pH levels. The highest (2.52 g) biomass was recorded by isolate NI₂ followed by NI₃ (2.23 g) and NI₁ (1.90 g), whereas lowest showed by NI₄ (0.87 g). Among the different pH levels, the isolates showed highest (1.97 g) biomass at 5.0 and 5.6 pH level (1.89 g), whereas the minimum (1.31 g) was observed at pH 9.0. In case of interaction combinations between different pH levels and isolates of district Peshawar, the maximum biomass (2.20 g) was recorded in case of isolate PI₂ at 5.0 level of pH followed by PI₁ and PI₅ (2.0 g) at pH level 5.6, whereas the lowest was observed in case of PI₄ (0.93 g) at 9.0 pH. The isolate PI₁ was found to be efficient in utilizing all the pH levels (5.0, 5.6 and 9.0) by exhibiting biomass of 1.80 g, 2.0 g and 1.57 g at 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 levels of pH (Table 4).

In case of interaction combinations between isolates of district Nowshera and different pH levels, all the isolates showed maximum biomass at every pH levels. The isolate NI₂ showed highest (2.97 g, 2.50 g and 2.10 g) biomass at 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 pH level, while the isolate NI₃ showed 2.53 g and 2.37 g of biomass at 5.0 and 5.6 pH. The isolate NI₄ showed lowest (0.50 g) biomass at a pH level of 9.0. In interaction combinations, the isolate showed maximum biomass at 5.0 and 5.6 as compared to 9.0 level of pH.

Effect of different pH levels on spore concentration

Significant ($P < 0.05$) effect of different pH levels was observed on spore concentration per ml. Among the different isolates, the highest (3.23×10^6) spore

Table 3. Effect of different pH levels on colony diameter (mm) of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani* after ten (10) days of incubation.

Districts	Isolates	pH levels			Mean
		5.0	5.6	9.0	
Peshawar	PI ₁	70.00 H	80.00 D	68.00 I	72.67 E
	PI ₂	75.00 F	70.22 H	*65.00 J	70.07 F
	PI ₃	74.44 F	70.47 GH	*63.00 K	69.30 FG
	PI ₄	64.75 J	78.00 E	63.00 K	68.58 G
	PI ₅	72.00 G	75.16 F	61.37 L	69.51 FG
Nowshera	NI ₁	83.78 C	81.00 D	70.00 H	78.26 C
	NI ₂	100.00 A	100.00 A	90.00 B	96.67 A
	NI ₃	85.00 C	80.00 D	77.28 E	80.76 B
	NI ₄	62.33 KL	59.67 M	51.67 N	57.89 H
	NI ₅	80.00 D	76.89 E	72.00 G	76.30 D
	Mean	76.73 A	77.14 A	68.13 B	74.00
	LSD for Isolates (I)	0.93			
	LSD for Treatments (T)	0.51			
	LSD for I×T	1.62			
	CV (%)	1.34			

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhi Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

Table 4. Effect of different pH levels on biomass (g) of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani* after 15 days of incubation.

Districts	Isolates	pH levels			Mean
		5.0	5.6	9.0	
Peshawar	PI ₁	1.80 GH	2.0 EF	1.57 IJ	1.79 DE
	PI ₂	2.20 CD	1.90 FG	1.17 K	1.76 E
	PI ₃	1.90 FG	1.70 HI	1.0 KL	1.53 F
	PI ₄	1.13 K	1.50 J	0.93 L	1.19 G
	PI ₅	1.61 J	2.0 EF	1.0 KL	1.53 F
Nowshera	NI ₁	2.20 CD	2.10 DE	1.43 J	1.90 C
	NI ₂	2.97 A	2.50 B	2.10 DE	2.52 A
	NI ₃	2.53 B	2.37 BC	1.80 GH	2.23 B
	NI ₄	1.17 K	0.93 L	0.50 M	0.87 H
	NI ₅	2.20 CD	1.90 FG	1.57 IJ	1.89 CD
	Mean	1.97 A	1.89 B	1.31 C	1.72
	LSD for Isolates (I)	0.11			
	LSD for Treatments (T)	0.06			
	LSD for I×T	0.19			
	CV (%)	6.84			

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhi Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

concentration (ml^{-1}) was recorded in case of isolate NI₂ followed by NI₃ (3.01×10^6) and NI₁ (2.51×10^6), whereas the lowest spore concentration (0.76×10^6) was recorded in case of isolate NI₄. The isolates showed maximum (2.29×10^6 and 2.16×10^6) spore production at pH level 5.0 and at 5.6, while the lowest spore concentration (1.62×10^6) was observed at pH 9.0. In case of interaction combinations between different pH levels and isolates of

district Peshawar, the highest (2.46×10^6) spore production was recorded in case of isolate PI₁ at pH level of 5.6 followed by PI₂ (2.32×10^6) and PI₁ (2.22×10^6) at pH 5.0. The lowest (0.75×10^6) spore production was recorded in case of isolate PI₄ at pH 9.0.

In case of interaction combinations between different pH levels and isolates of district Nowshera, the isolates showed maximum spore production almost at every pH

Table 5. Effect of different pH levels on spore concentration/ml of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani*.

Districts	Isolates	pH levels Spore concentration (10^6)			Mean
		5.0	5.6	9.0	
Peshawar	PI ₁	2.22 G	2.46 EF	1.91 H	2.20 D
	PI ₂	2.32 FG	1.96 H	1.41 I	1.90 E
	PI ₃	1.53 I	1.41 I	1.10 J	1.35 G
	PI ₄	1.45 I	1.64 I	0.75 KL	1.28 G
	PI ₅	1.64 I	1.91 H	0.98 JK	1.51 F
Nowshera	NI ₁	2.96 CD	2.60 E	1.98 H	2.51 C
	NI ₂	3.58 A	3.26 B	2.85 D	3.23 A
	NI ₃	3.26 B	3.18 BC	2.60 E	3.01 B
	NI ₄	1.10 J	0.74 L	0.43 M	0.76 H
	NI ₅	2.83 D	2.46 EF	2.22 G	2.50 C
	Mean	2.29 A	2.16 B	1.62 C	2.02
LSD for Isolates (I)		0.13×10 ⁶			
LSD for Treatments (T)		0.07×10 ⁶			
LSD for I×T		0.23×10 ⁶			
CV (%)		6.89			

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhri Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

Table 6. Effect of fungicides on colony diameter (mm) of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani* after five (5) days of incubation.

Districts	Isolates	Treatments				Mean
		Control	Aliette	Copper oxochloride	Dithane M-45	
Peshawar	PI ₁	60.00 E	56.67 FG	46.67 JK	5.00 S	42.08 C
	PI ₂	57.33 F	50.00 I	54.00 H	5.00 S	41.58 C
	PI ₃	54.00 H	50.00 I	37.33 O	0.00 T	35.33 E
	PI ₄	64.33 D	55.00 GH	48.00 J	8.00 R	43.83 E
	PI ₅	50.00 I	32.00 P	26.00 Q	0.00 T	27.00 G
Nowshera	NI ₁	75.00 B	60.00 E	42.00 M	0.00 T	44.25 D
	NI ₂	90.00 A	*90.00 A	*90.00 A	5.00 S	68.75 A
	NI ₃	70.00 C	50.00 I	45.00 KL	0.00 T	41.25 C
	NI ₄	42.00 M	25.00 Q	40.00 N	5.00 S	28.00 F
	NI ₅	60.00 E	43.33 LM	40.00 N	5.00 S	37.08 C
	Mean	62.27 A	51.20 B	46.90 C	3.30 D	40.92
LSD for Isolates (I)		0.93				
LSD for Treatments (T)		0.59				
LSD for I×T		1.85				
CV (%)		2.79				

*Resistant to fungicide.

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhri Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

level (5.0, 5.6 and 9.0). The isolate NI₂ exhibited highest (3.58×10^6 , 3.26×10^6 and 2.85×10^6) spore production at 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 level of pH, while the isolate NI₃ showed 3.26×10^6 and 3.18×10^6 spores at 5.0 and 5.6 level of pH. The least (0.43×10^6) spore production was recorded by NI₄ at pH level 9.0. In interaction combinations, the isolates showed highest spore production at 5.0 and 5.6

as compared to 9.0 level of pH (Table 5).

Effect of fungicides on colony diameter after five (5) days of incubation

The isolates showed significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in

Figure 5 (E) Figure showing effect of three fungicides (control, Aliette, Copper oxychloride and Dithane M-45) on colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *F. solani* on PDA after five (5) days of incubation at 25 °C collected from different locations of District Peshawar.

Figure 6 (F) Figure showing effect of three fungicides (control, Aliette, Copper oxychloride and Dithane M-45) on colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *F. solani* on PDA after five (5) days of incubation at 25 °C collected from different locations of District Nowshera.

mycelia growth at 1000 ppm of fungicides. The maximum (68.75 mm) colony diameter was recorded in isolate NI₂, followed by NI₁ (44.25 mm) and PI₄ (43.83 mm), while the lowest (27.00 mm) was accomplished by PI₅ (Table 6). All the isolates were found susceptible to T₃ by exhibiting minimum (3.30 mm) radial colony diameter than T₂ (46.90 mm) and T₁ (51.20 mm) as compared to T₀ (62.27 mm). In case of interactions between different fungicides and isolates of district Peshawar, the minimum (56.67 mm

and 55.00 mm) inhibition in radial colony growth as compared to T₀ (60.00 mm and 64.33 mm) was observed by the isolate PI₁ and PI₄ in T₁ followed by isolate PI₂ (54.00 mm) in T₂ as compared to T₀ (57.33 mm). The complete inhibition in radial colony growth was exhibited by isolate PI₃ and PI₅ by observing zero growth (Fig. 4.5).

In case of interaction combinations between different fungicides and isolates of district Nowshera, the isolate NI₂ was found resistant to T₁ and T₂ by observing same

Table 7. Effect of fungicides on colony diameter (mm) of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani* after ten (10) days of incubation.

Districts	Isolates	Treatments				Mean
		Control	Aliette	Copper oxychloride	Dithane M-45	
Peshawar	PI ₁	90.00 B	85.00 E	65.00 J	5.00 P	61.25 D
	PI ₂	87.33 CD	75.00 H	79.00 G	5.00 P	61.58 D
	PI ₃	86.33 CDE	80.00 FG	47.33 N	0.00 Q	53.42 F
	PI ₄	86.00 CDE	80.00 FG	73.67 H	43.67 O	70.83 B
	PI ₅	88.00 BC	54.67 L	59.00 K	0.00 Q	50.42 G
Nowshera	NI ₁	90.00 B	86.00 CDE	82.00 F	0.00 Q	64.50 C
	NI ₂	100.00 A	*100.00 A	*100.00 A	5.00 P	76.25 A
	NI ₃	85.67 DE	81.33 F	60.00 K	0.00 Q	56.75 E
	NI ₄	65.00 J	50.00 M	60.00 K	5.00 P	45.00 H
	NI ₅	68.33 I	60.00 K	65.00 J	5.00 P	49.58 G
	Mean	84.67 A	75.20 B	69.10 C	6.87 D	58.96

LSD for Isolates (I)	1.13
LSD for Treatments (T)	0.71
LSD for I×T	2.25
CV (%)	2.35

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhi Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

radial colony growth as in T₀ (90.00 mm). The least (60.00 mm and 50.00 mm) inhibition in radial colony growth was observed by NI₁ and NI₃ in T₁ as compared to T₀ (75.00 mm and 70.00 mm) while the complete inhibition in radial colony growth was measured by NI₁ and NI₃ by observing no growth in T₃. In interaction combinations, the highest inhibition in radial colony growth was measured in T₃ as compared to T₁ and T₂ (Figure 6).

Effect of fungicides on colony diameter after ten (10) days of incubation

Significant differences ($P < 0.05$) in colony diameter of *F. Solani* isolates (Table 7) were observed in response to different fungicides. The maximum (76.25 mm) colony diameter was recorded by NI₂, followed by PI₄ (70.83 mm) and NI₁ (64.50 mm), whereas the lowest was observed by NI₄ (45.00 mm). The isolates were found susceptible to T₃ with minimum (6.87 mm) colony diameter than T₂ (69.10 mm) and T₁ (75.20 mm) as compared to T₀ (84.67 mm). In case of interaction combinations between isolates of district Peshawar and different fungicides application, the minimum (85.00 mm) inhibition in radial colony growth was measured by the isolate PI₁, followed by PI₃ and PI₄ (80.00 mm) as compared to T₀ (90.00 mm, 86.33 mm and 86.00 mm) in treatment T₁. The minimum (79.00 mm) inhibition in radial colony growth was measured by PI₂ as compared to T₀ (87.33 mm) in T₂ whereas complete inhibition was

measured by PI₃ and PI₅ by observing zero growth in T₃ (Figure 7).

In case of interactions between isolates of district Nowshera and different fungicides application, the isolate NI₂ was found resistant to T₁ and T₂ by observing radial colony growth same as in T₀ (100.00 mm) and lowest (86.00 mm and 81.33 mm) inhibition in radial colony growth was measured by isolate NI₁ and NI₃ as compared to T₀ (90.00 mm and 85.67 mm) in T₁. The minimum (82.00 mm) inhibition in radial colony growth was measured by isolate NI₁ as compared to T₀ (90.00 mm). Complete inhibition was measured by isolate NI₁ and NI₃ by observing no growth in T₃. In interaction combinations, the maximum inhibition in radial colony growth was measured in T₃ as compared to T₁ and T₂ (Figure 8).

Effect of fungicides on biomass (g) after 15 days of incubation

Significant differences in fresh fungal biomass were observed as compared to untreated check (control). The highest (2.08 g) biomass was recorded in case of NI₂, followed by NI₁ (1.86 g) and PI₄ (1.81 g) while the lowest was recorded in case of NI₄ (0.68 g). The isolates were found susceptible to T₃ with the lowest biomass of 0.24 g than T₁ (1.54 g) and T₂ (1.55 g) as compared to T₀ (2.18 g). In case of interaction combinations between fungicides and isolates of district Peshawar, the minimum inhibition (2.10 g and 1.80 g) in biomass was recorded in

Figure 7 (G) Figure showing effect of three fungicides (Control, Aliette, Copper oxychloride and Dithane M-45) on colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *F. solani* on PDA after ten (10) days of incubation at 25°C collected from different locations of District Peshawar.

Figure 8 (H) Figure showing effect of three fungicides (Control, Aliette, Copper oxychloride and Dithane M-45) on colony diameter (mm) of five isolates of *F. solani* on PDA after ten (10) days of incubation at 25°C collected from different locations of District Nowshera.

isolate PI₄ and PI₁ in T₁ as compared to T₀ (2.43 g and 2.20 g) followed by PI₂ by exhibiting 1.80 g of biomass as compared to T₀ (2.30 g). The complete inhibition of in mycelia growth was recorded in isolate PI₃ and PI₅ in T₃.

In interaction combinations between fungicides and isolates of district Nowshera, the isolate NI₂ gave minimum (2.30 g and 2.54 g) inhibition in mycelia growth

as compared to T₀ (3.07) in T₁ and T₂. The isolate NI₁ exhibited 2.43 g and 2.20 g of biomass in T₁ and T₂ as compared to T₀ (2.81 g), whereas complete inhibition was recorded by isolate NI₁ and NI₃ in T₃ by observing no growth. In interaction combinations, the maximum inhibition by the isolates was recorded in T₃ as compared to T₁ and T₂ (Table 8).

Table 8. Effect of fungicides on biomass (g) of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani* after 15 days of incubation.

Districts	Isolates	Treatments				Mean
		Control	Aliette	Copper oxychloride	Dithane M-45	
Peshawar	PI ₁	2.20 DEF	1.80 K	1.60 JK	0.20 PQ	1.38 C
	PI ₂	2.30 CDE	1.60 JK	1.80 HIJ	0.30 P	1.50 C
	PI ₃	2.00 FGH	1.50 K	1.00 LM	0.00 Q	1.13 D
	PI ₄	2.43 CD	2.10 EFG	1.70 IJK	1.00 LM	1.81 B
	PI ₅	1.84 G-J	0.80 MN	1.20 L	0.00 Q	0.96 E
Nowshera	NI ₁	2.81 AB	2.43 CD	2.20 DEF	0.00 Q	1.86 B
	NI ₂	3.07 A	*2.30 CDE	*2.54 BC	0.43 OP	2.08 A
	NI ₃	2.10 EFG	1.50 K	1.20 L	0.00 Q	1.20 D
	NI ₄	1.15 L	0.60 NO	0.80 MN	0.20 PQ	0.68 F
	NI ₅	1.90 GHI	1.10 L	1.50 K	0.30 P	1.20 D
	Mean	2.18 A	1.54 B	1.55 B	0.24 C	1.38
LSD for Isolates (I)		1.15				
LSD for Treatments (T)		0.09				
LSD for I×T		0.29				
CV (%)		13.00				

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhi Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

Table 9. Effect of fungicides on spore concentration/ml of ten different isolates of *Fusarium solani*.

Districts	Isolates	Treatments				Mean
		Spore concentration (10 ⁶)				
		Control	Aliette	Copper oxychloride	Dithane M-45	
Peshawar	PI ₁	2.25 DE	1.76 F	1.55 H	0.04 O	1.40 DE
	PI ₂	2.35 D	1.46 HI	1.78 F	0.05 O	1.41 D
	PI ₃	1.07 K	1.30 IJ	1.07 K	0.00 O	1.06 F
	PI ₄	2.17 E	1.84 F	1.34 I	0.69 LMN	1.51 C
	PI ₅	1.58 GH	0.73 LM	0.86 L	0.00 O	0.79
Nowshera	NI ₁	2.66 C	2.16 E	1.85 F	0.00 O	1.67 B
	NI ₂	3.41 A	*2.61 C	*2.88 B	0.09 O	2.25 A
	NI ₃	2.16 E	1.75 FG	1.34 I	0.00 O	1.31 E
	NI ₄	1.12 K	0.65 MN	0.52 N	0.02 O	0.58 H
	NI ₅	1.83 F	1.13 JK	1.34 I	0.03 O	1.08 F
	Mean	2.14 A	1.54 B	1.45 C	0.09	1.31
LSD for Isolates (I)		0.09×10 ⁶				
LSD for Treatments (T)		0.05×10 ⁶				
LSD for I×T		0.18×10 ⁶				
CV (%)		8.24				

Isolates code;

Acheni Payan (PI₁), Palosi (PI₂), Chamkani (PI₃), Jogian (PI₄), Budhni (PI₅), Akberpura (NI₁), Garhi Momin (NI₂), Zakhi Charbagh (NI₃), Balu (NI₄), Tarru Jabba (NI₅).

Values followed by same letter (s) are not significantly different from one another at 5% level of significance.

Effect of fungicides on spore concentration per ml

Significant effects of fungicides were observed on per ml of spore concentration. Among different isolates, the highest (2.25×10⁶) spore production was recorded in isolate NI₂, followed by NI₁ (1.67×10⁶) and PI₄ (1.51×10⁶), whereas the lowest ml⁻¹ spore concentration (0.58×10⁶)

was recorded in case of NI₄. The highest inhibition in spore production (0.09×10⁶) was recorded in T₃ than T₂ (1.45×10⁶) and T₁ (1.54×10⁶) as compared to T₀ (2.14×10⁶). In case of interaction combinations between fungicides and isolates of district Peshawar, the minimum (1.76×10⁶ and 1.78×10⁶) inhibition in spore production was recorded by isolate PI₁ and PI₃ in T₁ and T₂ as

compared to T_0 (2.25×10^6 and 2.35×10^6). The complete inhibition in spore production was recorded by PI_3 and PI_5 in T_3 .

In interaction combinations between fungicides and isolates of district Nowshera, the minimum (2.88×10^6 and 2.61×10^6) inhibition in spore production was recorded in NI_2 in T_2 and T_1 as compared to T_0 (3.41×10^6), while the complete inhibition was recorded in NI_1 and NI_3 by observing zero growth in T_3 . In interaction combinations, the maximum inhibition in spore production was recorded in T_3 as compared to T_1 and T_2 (Table 9).

DISCUSSION

Okra plants are attacked by a number of soil borne fungi and among them *Fusarium solani*, the causal organism of root rot is considered as the most destructive pathogen, as the disease appears at seedling stage. Since okra is a summer vegetable crop and the fungus also favours higher soil temperatures, the disease causes severe losses. The fungus is highly adaptable to different environmental conditions due to which high variations exist among the isolates. As far as better management is concerned, the characterization of the isolates is necessary to help manage this menace in a better way. In the present study, a survey was conducted to find out the disease distribution of ten different okra growing regions of district Peshawar and Nowshera, and also the various isolates of *Fusarium solani* were assessed by evaluating the *in vitro* effect of different pH levels and the efficacy of fungicides.

The disease was distributed in different areas of district Peshawar and Nowshera and was found most severe in areas of district Nowshera with the maximum seedling mortality. The disease may be severe due to poor cultural practices and climatic factors such as plant spacing and higher soil temperatures. It is evident from the previous studies that cultural and climatic factors favors the disease (Aviles *et al.*, 2003). This study was further supported by Malvick (2002) that the disease is favoured by higher soil temperature and moderate soil moisture.

The isolates of *F. solani* were found significantly different by their characterization at different pH levels *in vitro*. The isolates grew best at 5.0 and 5.6 level of pH as compared to 9.0. These results were supported by Gupta *et al.*, (2010) that isolates of *F. solani* isolated from guava were observed highly variable by their assessment at different pH levels. It was also reported that all the isolates showed maximum colony growth at 5.0 and 5.5 than 8.0 level of pH. These results are also in line with the results of Khilari and Ahmed *et al.*, (2004) and Gandhara *et al.*, (2004). There were some isolates that were found very efficient in utilizing the 5.0, 5.6 and 9.0 level of pH. Similar results were reported by Gandhara *et al.*, (2004) that among various isolates of *F. oxysporum*,

an isolate showed maximum growth in 5.0, 6.0 and 9.0 level of pH. This was further supported by Caracuel *et al.*, (1993) that isolates of *F. oxysporum* showed maximum growth on basic medium due to the expression of *ena1* gene which activated by the higher concentrations of Na^+ and was responsible to regulate the internal environment of the fungus by regulating constant condition of pH. These results are in harmony with the findings of Jamaria (1972), that strains of *Fusarium solani* grow well on a wide range of pH ranging from 3.2 to 8.3.

The isolates of *F. solani* showed variable responses to the effect of different fungicides. The isolates were found most susceptible to Dithane M-45 and was proved to be the best fungicide in controlling the pathogen. Similarly Ahmed *et al.*, (2012) reported that the complete inhibition in mycelial growth was observed by Dithane M-45. These results were further supported by Nisa *et al.*, (2011) and Mamza *et al.*, (2008) and Rajput *et al.*, (2012). The isolates were found less sensitive to Aliette and Copper oxychloride. However, some isolates were found resistant to Aliette and Copper oxychloride. This may be due to the selection pressure of particular fungicides which lead to the development of resistant genes. Similar results were reported by Rajput *et al.*, (2012) that copper oxychloride was found less effective fungicide in controlling *F. solani*. Amanda and Bruce, (1996) suggested Aliette as the less effective fungicide in controlling the *F. Oxysporum*, and the fungicide may be effected at higher concentrations. However some isolates were found very less sensitive to Aliette.

The present results are in close proximity with the findings of Maitlo *et al.*, 2013 who reported seven fungicides which were applied at three different concentrations. All the fungicides inhibited the colony growth of *Fusarium solani*. But the contact fungicide (Dithane M-45) proved to be most efficient, showed complete inhibition of *Fusarium solani* followed by Aliette and Copper oxychloride at 100,150 and 50 ppm concentration.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

1. The disease was distributed in different locations and were found most severe with highest percent seedling mortality in district Nowshera.
2. The isolates were found significantly different by their characterization at different pH levels. The isolates showed maximum radial colony growth at 5.0 and 5.6 level of pH as compared to 9.0. However, some isolates were found very efficient in utilizing all the pH levels.
3. *In vitro*, all the isolates were found most susceptible to Dithane M-45 whereas less susceptible to Aliette and Copper oxychloride.

Recommendations

1. A detail study is required for the confirmation of variations that exists among the various isolates of *F. solani* by using other factors like growth in different media, temperature.
2. The alkaline soils are recommended to grow the crop but not highly alkaline which locks up nutrients in the soil.
3. Dithane M-45 is recommended an effective fungicide for the *in vitro* management of *F. solani*.

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